

**SAVINGS BANK ACCOUNT HOLDERS DEPEND MORE ON
 ATM: A STUDY RELATED TO MANGALURU CITY
 CORPORATION**

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Abstract:

Every individual is busy in his/her schedule. Each and every transaction need not be done during banking working hours. ATM cum debit card made the customers not to wait for their money. ATM centers have been operating by many banks at nook and corner. In this view, major 13 banks such as SBI, Corporation Bank, Canara Bank, ICICI, Karnataka Bank, SBM, Vijaya Bank, HDFC, Indian Bank, Indian Overseas Bank, Syndicate Bank, Bank of India, and Bank of Baroda operating in Mangaluru City Corporation were considered. Intensity of ATM and its use is studied in Mangaluru City Corporation area.

Key Words: SMS, Currency Denominations, Notes Detector & High Pixel Camera

Introduction:

Savings Bank Account is an everyday need for a common man. Money transaction starts in bank through SB Account. From school level one can open Bank Account and savings culture is cultivated. When one becomes citizen, bank accounts help to do umpteen transactions. Banks made transaction very easy by making use of ATM as debit card also. SB Account holders are using it many times according to their need. Employees depend more on ATM than cheques. Branchless banking and paperless banking is supported by customers reduce burden on banks.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the instant ATM use by Savings Bank Account holders
- ✓ To study the greater dependence on ATM as a branchless banking

Limitations:

Study is purely based on primary data. Only 50 samples were taken at random considering the opinion of both men and women employees who operate their ATMs and SB account in Mangaluru City Corporation area. 13 banks and its branches were covered. Analysis was made based on the opinions of the respondents which were collected in the month of October 2016. There is a scope for further study.

Analysis:

- ✓ Out of 50 respondents, there were 28 male and 22 female. Among them 4 student employees. 28 private employees, 11 Govt. employees in teaching, 7 Govt. employees in non-teaching. 22 respondents earn below Rs. 10000. 12 respondents each earn Rs. 25000 and Rs. 50000 respectively. Only 4 respondents earn above Rs 50000 as their monthly income. These categories were made to know the behavior of SB account holders in using ATMs. All the 50 respondents had SB Accounts in different Banks.
- ✓ This study was made to cover maximum number of banks that are available in Mangaluru City Corporation. In a survey, major 13 banks such as SBI, Corporation Bank, Canara Bank, ICICI, Karnataka Bank, SBM, Vijaya Bank, HDFC, Indian Bank, Indian Overseas Bank, Syndicate Bank, Bank of India, and Bank of Baroda operating in Mangaluru City Corporation were considered. Their branches were located in different areas of Mangaluru City Corporation.
- ✓ Frequency of ATM use:

Monthly Use	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Number of Respondents	6	10	8	7	10	1	1	2	nil	5

Majority of respondents frequently used their ATM for their transactions. It shows that how ATM attracted the customer and made their transaction easy. All the respondents supported branchless banking and paperless banking.

- ✓ 17 respondents used the ATM of same bank. They were very concerned about the service charges. They were careful about their card use. 33 respondents knew about additional charges, but they thought about their emergency needs. Hardly 5 times in a month they used it in other branches of bank.
- ✓ 7 respondents faced certain problems while using their ATM. But all problems were solved within a week.
- ✓ 2 respondents got torn notes in ATM. But still every respondent depend more on ATM.

- ✓ No respondents received fake notes in ATM. It shows that a common man can rely on ATM while doing transactions.
- ✓ 38 respondents had the facility of getting SMS from their banks for their ATM transactions. Still 12 did not know about this facility and hence they were not getting SMS from bank.
- ✓ Respondents were careful about their other transactions. Hardly 6 respondents used it for transfer of funds. 44 respondents used it for balance enquiry and withdrawals only.
- ✓ Only 50% of respondents were used it as debit card at their shopping centre. Others did not want to use it for their purchase transactions.
- ✓ Even though the bank has opened many ATM centers, few centers were crowded and 19 respondents faced problem of waiting in a queue.
- ✓ Since number of ATMs is more, hence respondents depended more on ATM and bank has freed to maximum extent in clearing cheques at their counter. Only 9 respondents used cheques for cash payments and others have drawn amount through ATM to clear off their payments.
- ✓ 7 respondents used cheques incase of below withdrawal limit of ATM and 8 respondents used it for above withdrawal limit.

Suggestions:

Respondents wanted some changes in present ATM system. From this point of view suggestions were made.

- ✓ Let there be option to get their currency denominations in the machine for Rs. 50, Rs.100, Rs. 500 and so on. So that customers can have their required currency notes.
- ✓ There should be option to take at least 5 times in a year the exceeding limit up to the extent of Rs. 50000.
- ✓ As soon as the ATM machine is out of order, repairs should be made immediately by the concerned authorities.
- ✓ When ATM does not have enough money, it should give indication to the ATM operator as ATM does not have required money.
- ✓ If one ATM is not working, it should indicate the nearest location or the Bank should give SMS to have this facility.
- ✓ All the ATM centers should have proper camera system. Camera should have high pixel capacity with clarity in face reading. Camera should be monitored and be connected to internet facility. Warning signal operation is to be fitted to get alarming sound through internet at the required destination.
- ✓ ATM compartment is to be closed as soon as one account holder uses ATM.
- ✓ There should be only one use inside the ATM center to avoid the mishap in respect of pin number.
- ✓ There should be uniformity in Machine and its operation. Bank has to send SMS to concerned SB account holder for their every transaction.
- ✓ RBI has to insist the inserting authorities to insert new and perfect notes in order to avoid soiled and torn notes use.
- ✓ Fake notes, mutilated and torn notes, soiled and imperfect notes detector is to be installed in all ATM centers.
- ✓ There should be facility to upload the deposits also.

References:

1. Field survey in Mangaluru City Corporation Area in October, 2016